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Developing Teachers' Social Competences, an Imperative of Contemporary Society

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Abstract: Teachers' social competences are an imperative of contemporary society. The article demonstrates the importance of developing teachers' social intelligence, given the fact that social competences have a great impact on academic success. A high level of social intelligence helps teachers diffuse stress, instills feelings of efficacy, prevent isolation, and promote a positive self-image, especially in today's rapidly changing society, which makes teaching much more demanding. The article also illustrates the interrelation between emotional, social, and cognitive competences, which help teachers deal with their emotions and establish social climates of cooperation, thus promoting positive teacher-student relationships even in challenging social interactions with students.

Keywords: social intelligence, social competences, emotional competences, cognitive competences, future teachers.

Rezumat: *Competențele sociale ale profesorilor reprezintă un imperativ al societății contemporane. Articolul demonstrează importanța dezvoltării inteligenței sociale a profesorilor, dat fiind faptul că competențele sociale au un profund impact asupra succesului lor academic și asupra avansării în carieră. Un nivel ridicat de inteligență socială îi ajută pe profesori să reziste la stres, să demonstreze eficacitate, să capete o imagine de sine pozitivă în societatea contemporană, aflată în schimbare rapidă, ceea ce face predarea mult mai solicitantă. Articolul ilustrează interdependența dintre competențele emoționale, competențele sociale și competențele cognitive, care îi ajută pe profesori să facă față propriilor emoții, să stabilească un climat social de cooperare, promovând astfel relații pozitive dintre profesori și elevi și în cadrul interacțiunilor sociale provocatoare.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *inteligență socială, competențe sociale, competențe emoționale, competențe cognitive, viitoare cadre didactice.*

The pedagogical profession is about interactions and creating relationships with students, parents, colleagues, and all those involved in the educational environment. As a result, the success of a teacher's activity depends not only on his/her professional skills but also on his/her ability to deal and build constructive relationships with others.

Teachers' social competences are important for the mastering of the social challenges inherent in their profession and for building positive teacher-student relationships. Therefore, developing the teachers' social intelligence is crucial for their academic success. Research reveals that social interactions in the academic environment and the quality of the relationships the teachers have with their students are vital for both teachers' and students' cognitive, social, and affective-motivational development. Identifying the characteristics that support teachers in dealing with their own emotions and in promoting positive teacher-student relationships, even in challenging social interactions with students, is highly relevant for both student development and teachers' occupational well-being [1]. According to Marzano, Marzano, & Pickering (2003), the teachers that develop social intelligence skills tend to establish supportive and encouraging relationships with their students, developing lessons that are based on the students' strong points and abilities, creating and applying behavioral guidelines in ways that enhance intrinsic motivation [5]. Social competences help teachers avoid burnout and generate internal drivers that increase their well-being and create a supportive learning environment.

The definition of social intelligence has a long history and a broad conceptualization. H. J. Thorndik (1920) defined social intelligence as "the ability to act wisely in human relations". G.W. Allport (1937) viewed social intelligence as a person's ability to judge people correctly, predict their behavior, and ensure adequate adaptation in interpersonal relations. In the works of D. Wechsler (1943) social intelligence is understood as an individual's suitability for being a human – that is, the ability to cope well with life's situations. Guilford (1967) built on Thorndike's suggestion that "there is a social intelligence, apart from ordinary intelligence". He stated that "social intelligence is the awareness of attention, perceptions, thoughts, desires, feelings, etc. of others and ourselves". Weinstein (1969) speaks of social intelligence as "the ability to accomplish interpersonal

tasks". Keating (1978) mentions that for most of the time, psychometricians have conceptualized social intelligence as a separate set of primary mental abilities to be contrasted with the abilities of academic or formal intelligence. Sternberg (1981) views social intelligence as a component of general intelligence, while H.J. Eysenck (1985) said that it is the result of general intelligence under the influence of socio-cultural conditions. M.E. Ford and M.S. Tisak (1983) defined social intelligence as a group of mental abilities associated with the processing of social information for successful problem-solving. D.G. Myers (1995) defines social intelligence as social thinking, the ability to evaluate ourselves and others on the basis of social attitudes [4, 12].

Neisser (1976) emphasizes a relevant pragmatic goal that has brought forth a reconsideration of the importance of "social intelligence" as contrasted with "academic intelligence". However, recent studies demonstrate the interrelation between cognitive, emotional, and social intelligence. Björkqvist (2007) theorizes that components of social intelligence include perceptual, cognitive-analytical, and behavioral abilities or skills. Salovey & Pizarro (2003) mention that many competences associated with social intelligence rely on emotional intelligence, which includes skills in identifying, expressing, understanding, managing, and using emotions adaptively [6]. More recent studies denote an increasing interest in social intelligence. For example, Jeungmin Lee, Jerald D. Kralik and Jaeseung Jeong (2018) consider the general architecture of social intelligence in the human mind and brain. Xavier Job et al. (2019) study the relationship of individual differences in a person's perception of spatial perspective with social intelligence. Anastasia Katou, Pawan Budhwar, and Charmi Patel (2020) note in their research that the social intelligence of a leader has a stronger positive influence on the creativity of subordinates compared to performance through exploitation [9].

The relevance of the study of social intelligence in future teachers as a condition for the development of their competence is defined as a tendency to develop scientific knowledge and existing needs of social practice [12]. The concept of *social competence* is understood as a set of social skills, knowledge, abilities, emotions, values, behavioral components, experiences, and perso-

nal beliefs, which allows a person to actively interact with society, various groups and individuals, to productively perform various social roles and optimize social relations, depending on the available social information. Based on a review of relevant literature, researchers have identified a list of social competences, namely: affection for others (an ability to love and trust); empathy (sensitivity, compassion, acceptance of others, recognition of their emotions); effective communication (effective response, choosing one's own answer, ability to listen to others); relationship management (an ability to understand and connect with others, to manage conflicts and accept responsibility) [11].

A recent scientific model of social intelligence was offered by Boyatzis, Gaskin, and Wei (2015), who describe the behavioral competences stemming from social intelligence as involving empathy, influence, conflict management, teamwork, systems thinking, and pattern recognition [2]. Boyatzis (1982) emphasizes the interrelation of competences, which appear in three clusters: (1) cognitive intelligence (CI) competences, such as systems thinking or pattern recognition; (2) emotional intelligence (EI) competences, such as adaptability, emotional self-control, self-confidence, initiative, emotional self-awareness, positive outlook, and achievement orientation; and (3) social intelligence (SI) competences, such as empathy, organizational awareness, inspirational leadership, influence, coaching and mentoring, conflict management (i.e., negotiation), and teamwork [3].

This model (Figure 1) illustrates the importance of the competences that appear in three clusters: cognitive intelligence, emotional intelligence, and social intelligence – leading to life satisfaction, career satisfaction, and career success. According to Jennings and Greenberg, teachers' social-emotional competence and their wellbeing affect classroom management. Teachers with high social and emotional competence are self-aware. They recognize their own emotions, they are able to use their emotions positively to motivate others to learn, and they understand their own capacities and emotional strengths and weaknesses particularly well. They are also socially aware, recognizing and understanding others' emotions, including those of their students and colleagues, and they work to build strong, supportive relationships.

Figure 1. *The model of CIF*

Teachers with high social and emotional competence also demonstrate prosocial values – they have deep respect for their colleagues, students, and student's families, and they care about how their own decisions affect the wellbeing of others [10].

The multifaceted view of intelligence as presented above facilitates the understanding of social behavior in academic settings. Social intelligence involves a number of different capabilities, special social habits, and attitudes [5]. Accentuating social intelligence, V. Taborsky notes that social competences imply a flexibility in behavior in the social sphere that is based on information received from outside. The more information a person possesses, the better he/she will behave in society [11]. Holy Grail (1970) defined teaching competency as "the teacher attributes and teacher characteristics that determinate the teachers' efficiency and effectiveness" [7]. A high level of social intelligence could be immediately protective and promote resilience through effective competences that can help to diffuse stress, instill feelings of efficacy, prevent isolation, and promote a positive self-image [6]. These competen-

Figure 2. *The Prosocial Classroom Model*

ces are developed to help the teachers and the students to establish social climates of cooperation, a setting in which students and adults can learn together, play together, and build a quality relationship [5].

To conclude: Developing teachers' social intelligence becomes a necessity in modern society. Albrecht (2006) considers social intelligence a prerequisite for teachers. He believes that the educational system and teachers should respect the rules and behaviors associated with high social intelligence. Teachers' social competences are the engine that boosts wellbeing and positive relationships in the academic environment. The skills that are developed through social competences are obtained through practical experiences, whose main focus is to increase productiveness not only in academic achievement, but also in social relationships. The importance of social competences for future teachers cannot be overestimated. A well-developed social competence that takes into account the peculiarities of information society allows a person, in particular a future teacher, to interact constructively with the social environment and to fulfill successfully professional responsibilities using information and communication technologies [11]. Thorndike (1920) stated that social intelligence increases with the age and experience of a person [5]. Therefore, the achievement of a successful career is a constructive growth of teachers' emotional, social and cognitive competences through experiences and social interaction.

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